

OPTIMIZATION OF PROJECT ACCELERATION SCHEDULING USING CRITICAL PATH METHOD (CPM) AND PROGRAM EVALUATION AND REVIEW TECHNIQUE (PERT):

A CASE STUDY OF HOUSING NUMBER B9 DM VILLAGE BANGUNTAPAN

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Abstract. Successful project management should prioritize the time duration of each project by scheduling project activities. This type of research used the qualitative as a research method. The object of this research is house number B9 in DM Banguntapan Village. This research aims to optimize project timeline for project construction in DM Village Banguntapan using critical evaluation methods. For this study, we analyzed data collected from observation, interview, and documentation techniques. We used an established sequential technique, namely critical path method (CPM) and program evaluation and review technique (PERT). The results show that the critical path of the project is found in activities A-B-C-D-F-G-H-I-J-K-L-M-N-O-V-X-Y-Z. The duration of completion of the critical path in the CPM method is 173 days, while in the PERT method is 141.83 days. The crashing projection results show that the critical path can be accelerated to 107 days with a total additional cost of 9,285,310 IDR. The S-curve can provide an indicator that the overall project acceleration duration is 168 days at a cost of 320,763,134 IDR. The probability from the Z table shows a percentage of 99%, which means that the completion of the critical path is very likely. Importantly, There are several limitations in time and cost optimization based on the critical path determination scenario. The main limitation is the lack of other scheduling methods. This study can be a reference for the best planning to be applied to all sectors

.Keywords: *Project management; project scheduling; CPM method; PERT method*

1 INTRODUCTION

The property and real estate sector is considered capable of providing significant capacity in driving national economic growth in Indonesia (I, D Adelia et al., 2023). The index of commercial property and real estate supply in Indonesia at the beginning of the first quarter of 2023 grew by 9.35% year on year. In the third quarter of 2023, the investment value and performance of the property and real estate industry sector experienced positive growth of 6.22% from the first quarter of 2023 (Bank Indonesia, 2022). In this regard, Property and real estate development projects such as construction projects, infrastructure projects, and housing construction and development projects have a significant impact on increasing national economic growth (Jamal et al., 2023). Basically, project realization involves many stages in the project management process such as the planning stage, development stage, and implementation stage.

Scheduling errors and unrealistic deadlines are caused by poor planning due to oversimplification and omission of activities (Tomczak & Jaskowski, 2020). In this case, planning a housing development project becomes a basic reference before stepping into the realization stage of the actual housing project. Housing development planning aims to ensure that the project can run regularly and be completed at the specified time. Importantly, project scheduling planning is related to project control risks such as time duration mismatches in completing housing development projects. Delays in the completion of housing construction projects cause moral and material losses (Elizabeth et al., 2020). The main reason for managing project scheduling risks is to ensure that deadlines can be achieved appropriately (Kholil et al., 2018).

Previous studies show that managers face many challenges when they handle construction projects. Factors that increase their unpredictability include weather vulnerability to the construction process, design uniqueness, high employee turnover rates, various logistical issues related to supply, and high project failure rates (Michał Tomczak, 2019). The construction of house number B9 in DM Village Banguntapan only uses the expert judgment and analogous estimating. Analogous estimating is the process of analogizing to previous project development activities by changing project activity parameters such as duration, man-hours, and number of employees (Astari et al., 2021; Oka & Kartikasari, 2019).

The obstacles faced in the process of working on the house construction project at DM Village Banguntapan are weather factors such as the rainy season. In addition, there is no structured scheduling in the process of building houses. In general, these constraints and obstacles will affect time estimates such as time lags in the construction of housing projects. Based on these problems, researchers are interested in conducting further research related to effective scheduling scenarios for the sustainability of housing construction project number B9 at DM Village Banguntapan. In addition, researchers also provide an overview related to project acceleration using the Critical Path Method (CPM) and Project Evaluation Review and Techniques (PERT) methods.

Successful project management should prioritize the time duration of each project by scheduling project activities. Interestingly, scheduling must consider the stages systematically so that the project objectives can be achieved optimally (Lubis et al., 2021). Network planning is one of the methods developed to obtain perfect scheduling. Critical Path Method (CPM) and Program Evaluation Review and Technique (PERT) are two fundamental approaches used in network planning. PERT is a probabilistic schedule determination method, while CPM is a deterministic

schedule determination method. Accordingly, the objective of the research is to determine a more efficient method of scheduling a house construction project using the CPM and PERT methods through determining the critical path. Thus, this research aims to ensure that all work can be done in a structured manner and not waiting for each other between one job and another.

2 LITERATURE REVIEW & HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

Operational Management

Operational management is an activity that aims to maximize the management of available resources as an effort in transformation so as to produce an output that has many benefits from the previous process. Operational management is a process where all elements of production factors are used optimally and maximally such as optimizing the elements of labor, machinery, equipment, raw materials, and others (Ambarwati & Supardi, 2020). Indeed, operational management can be formulated as a series of actions or activities that can produce value in the form of products or services by changing the input and output processes. In line with this statement, operational management can be defined as a process or activity of creating products in the form of goods or services by converting inputs into outputs by organizing and coordinating the use of resources effectively and efficiently (Kristanto et al., 2022). Furthermore, the scope of operational management includes output planning, transformation process design, capacity planning, plant construction planning, facility layout planning, workflow design, inventory management, project management, scheduling, quality control, and reliability in quality maintenance.

Project Management

Project management is an activity that includes planning, organizing, and supervising all activities and resources managed to achieve the objectives of the process to be carried out (Dewi et al., 2023). Project management is formulated as a way to complete a project by stimulating the components of cost management, time management, risk management, and quality management (Sitanggang et al., 2019). Project management essentially only provides the concepts, frameworks, methods, and tools to implement change effectively. Project management has aspects among the foundations of theoretical guidelines mainly in the fields of economics, sociology, and psychology. In addition, differences in theoretical guidelines may lead to an imbalance between interpersonal trust, inter-organizational trust, and intra-organizational trust (Cerić et al., 2021). The main objective of the project management process is to ensure that project work can be implemented in a timely, structured, efficient manner, and achieve the expected results. Thus,

Project Scheduling

Project scheduling is one part of planning that can provide information about project schedules, activities, and progressivity by utilizing resource performance such as cost, labor, and project duration. Project scheduling can help determine the priority relationship between each activity, identify the priority relationship between each activity, and show realistic time estimates for each activity. Project scheduling is an important component as it provides insight into the progress of the project regarding personnel, equipment, materials, costs, and resource performance. It also helps with project planning and completion progress schedules (Perdana & Rahman, 2019). Scheduling is determined by the relationship between activities that are realized

in detail and accurately (Iluk et al., 2020). Therefore, project scheduling has a direct correlation with the intensity of activities to be started, postponed, and completed.

Critical Path Method (CPM)

Critical path method (CPM) serves to determine the critical path on the project. The critical path is the longest path through the network that contains the critical activities of the project (Adinugroho & Madelan, 2021). Critical Path Method (CPM) can provide information and projections related to the stages that will be needed in completing project scheduling. Critical path method (CPM) is a method that uses experience or scheduling time data to determine completion time. This method creates a critical path by using forward pass and backward pass calculations that can show activities that must be completed on time (Ramdani et al., 2022). Determining the critical path using the critical path method (CPM) can be a solution step to solve problems related to scheduling, especially in time projection. Therefore, critical path method (CPM) is very important to minimize project delays (Nurul & Rani, 2023).

Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT)

Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT) aims to find project scenarios based on the possibility of achieving the planned journey according to the schedule (Yuwono et al., 2021). This method uses a probabilistic perspective, which recognizes the unavoidable uncertainties during the project (Itani, 2023). PERT can explain the flow of the scheduling process so that critical paths can be identified in the scheduling process so that tasks can be completed quickly (Mezgebu & Reddy, 2021). Generally, PERT method is based on some basic assumptions such as activities, schedules, time estimation, work networks, critical networks, slack, probability of completion, and risk management. Optimistic time durations and pessimistic time durations are assumed to be the time durations that are most likely to occur or almost have the same occurrence in ongoing project activities (TAŞDEMİR, 2022).

Crashing Project

Crashing project is a method to accelerate the project duration by reducing the duration of each project activity that affects the project completion time (Salakory et al., 2023). The application of the crashing project method directly results in an increase in the estimation of direct costs and resources on the critical path. The crashing project method has several alternatives in its implementation such as additional labor procurement, additional overtime work, variations in working time. Interestingly, most the crashing project method is implemented at night because it aims to avoid excessive mobility during normal working hours (Farida & Anenda, 2022). Therefore, critical tasks can be completed faster than other tasks with the addition of more resources.

S-Curve

In the construction framework, the S-curve has been used as a project monitoring model to track project status and a guide for reporting progress in project management (Mohamad et al., 2021). The S-curve is a graph that represents the accumulation of all project

activities from the start of construction to completion. The S-curve graph visualization shows the extent to which the project has progressed and can be used as an attempt to optimize decision making options based on projected project results. Basically, the letter "S" pattern will be used to depict the cumulative cost and time graph of the construction project (Konior & Szóstak, 2020). In this regard, the advantage of the S-curve is that it selects a method that is easy to understand and can be used as a tool in the planning and communication process. However, the disadvantage of the S-curve is that it cannot identify or provide dependencies on the relationships between activities in the project (Phadnis & Torkkeli, 2022).

3 RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This type of research used the qualitative as a research method. Qualitative research was chosen in this research because this methods using descriptive systems with collaborate various approaches such as naturalism, anthropology, phenomenology, and case studies that are not limited to a narrow definition (Hameed, 2020). This study employs an case studies and integrative literature review based on previous study. The data handling procedure followed suggestions from previous research and review from expert judgment, especially by the project manager. The object of this research is house number B9 in DM Banguntapan Village. Content analysis involves collecting data through a variety of different research methods that are based on the type of data being collected (Kang & Hwang, 2021). For this study, we analyzed data collected from observation, interview, and documentation techniques. Data is analyzed by extracting meaning from the artifacts involved in verbal communication.

We analyzed the data as a function to determine the acceleration of the critical path of a housing construction project. The collection and analysis process has gone through many stages to reach a valid conclusion (Erlingsson & Brysiewicz, 2017; Sung, 2021). This investigation has four stages in the data analysis method. We used an established sequential technique, namely critical path method (CPM), program evaluation and review technique (PERT), crashing project, and S-curve. Clear logic and conceptual reasoning are the basis of our arguments and explanations of the methodology of this study. Finally, the results of this research were then written in field notes which were then analyzed using the scheduling method and written in the project scheduling evaluation description.

To investigate this statistically, we calculated the data formulations required by the critical path method (CPM) and program evaluation and review technique (PERT). The critical path can be determined by calculating the earliest start time, earliest completion time, latest start time, latest completion time (Nigam & Sharma, 2022). The additional advantage of using this calculation formulation is that maximizes the performance of the critical path method (CPM) and program evaluation and review technique (PERT) processes for determining duration values on critical path (Soyluk & İlerisoy, 2022). Subsequently, the calculation formulation below is used to obtain further data processing results.

a) Data processing using CPM method

The first step is to find the results of the forward calculation or find the values (TE, ES, and EF). The forward calculation is performed using formulas (1) and (2), which indicate that the forward calculation moves from the initial event to the final event.

	$TE(j) = TE(i, j) = 0$	(1)
	Equation 1. (TE) Expected Time	

	$EF(i,j) = ES(i,j) + t(i,j)$	(2)
	Equation 2. (EF) Early Finish; (ES) Early Start; (t) Time Duration	

After the forward calculation is complete, the next step is to perform the backward calculation. Backward calculation can be done with formulas (3) and (4). The purpose of backward calculation is to calculate the last, beginning, and end events of the last activity (TL, LS, and LF). This process moves from the last event to the first event. The following is the backward calculation formulation.

	$LS(i,j) = LF(i) - t(i,j)$	(3)
	Equation 3. (LS) Latest Start; (LF) Latest Finish; (t) Time Duration	
	$LF(i,j) = TL ; TL = TE$	(4)
	Equation 4. (LF) Latest Finish; (TL) Latest Time; (TE) Expected Time	

To determine the critical path, the next step is to calculate the total floating points and free floating points. Total float (5) is the amount of time that can be delayed to complete an activity without affecting the fastest time to complete the project as a whole (Soni et al., 2022). The critical path must have a total float value equal to zero. Free float (6) is the amount of time that can be used to complete an activity without affecting the start time of other activities or the fastest occurrence of other activities in the network (Bagshaw, 2021). Thus, the determination of the critical path must consider the calculation of the total float value of each project work.

	$TF = LF - ES - t$	(5)
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Equation 5. (TF) Total Float; (LF) Late Finish; (ES) Early Start; (t) Time Duration

	$FF = EF - ES - t$	(6)
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Equation 6. (FF) Free Float; (EF) Early Finish; (ES) Early Start; (t) Time Duration

a) Data processing using PERT method

The pert method has three time components such as optimistic time, most likely time, and pessimistic time (Masłowski et al., 2021). The critical path in the pert method is known as slack. Process of determining the critical path in the PERT method is done by calculating the time parameters of the relevant operating activities and the total duration of the operations (Chang et al., 2021). The following calculation formulation is used to determine

the expected average time value (7) of the three time components in the PERT method.

	$Mean (Te) = \frac{(To + 4(Tm) + Tp)}{6}$	(7)
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Equation 7. (TE) Expected Time; (To) Optimistic Time; (Tm) Most Likely Time; (Tp) Pessimistic Time

If the PERT method results show that the Free Slack (FS) and Total Slack (TS) values are equal to 0, then critical path identification can be carried out. Furthermore, calculation of variance (8) and standard deviation (9) can be done if the identification of the critical path in the PERT method has been successful. The following calculation formulation is used to determine the variance and standard deviation values of the PERT method.

	$V = \sum (PERT\ Critical\ Path)$	(8)
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	$Std = \sqrt{Variance\ Critical\ Path}$	(9)
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Equation 8,9. (V) Variance; (Std) Standard Deviation

If the variance and standard deviation results have been determined, the next step is to calculate the Z value score. The Z value score aims to calculate the probability of completion of construction risk time by using the deviation formula (10).

	$Z = \frac{Td - \sum (Te\ PERT)}{Std}$	(10)
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Equation 10. (Z) Z Value Score; (Td) Time Duration; (Te) Expected Time; (Std) Standard Deviation

4. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

Critical Path Method (CPM)

This suggests that there are a total of 26 jobs or activities with the duration of each activity. The total duration of the entire set of works obtained is 200 days or 6.5 months. Furthermore, the project time duration and predecessor activities that have been found will support the critical activities that must be passed in the project. This is an important finding in the understanding of the scheduling planning using critical path method (CPM). The duration of the project and activities along with their predecessors are shown in table 1.

Table 1. Project activities and duration

No	Code	Activity	Predecessors	Duration (Days)
1	A	Land Clearing and Leveling	-	1
2	B	Sketch and Bouwplank Work	A	1

3	C	Chicken Claw Work	B	3
4	D	Foundation and Concrete Plate Work	C	8
5	E	Network Pipe Installation	D	2
6	F	Sloof and Beam Work (1st Floor)	D	9
7	G	Brick and Frame Installation (1st Floor)	D,F	13
8	H	Dak Installation (2nd Floor)	G	10
9	I	Stair Structure Installation	H	7
10	J	Brick and Frame Installation (2nd Floor)	I	13
11	K	Concrete Gutter Installation	I,J	8
12	L	Light Steel Roof Installation	K	10
13	M	Tile Installation	L	13
14	N	Electrical Installation (1st and 2nd floor)	M	5
15	O	PDAM Water Installation	N	3
16	P	Plastering (1st floor and 2nd floor)	I,G,J	13
17	Q	Plastering / Painting (1st floor and 2nd floor)	P	10
18	R	Ceiling Installation (1st floor and 2nd floor)	Q	10
19	S	Ceiling Paint (1st and 2nd Floor)	R	4
20	T	Ceramic Installation (1st and 2nd Floor)	S	13
21	U	Wall Paint	P,Q	11
22	V	Septic Tank and Ground Tank Installation	E,O,U	4
23	W	Garage Construction	V	10
24	X	Ceramic Garage Installation	W	6
25	Y	Canopy Installation	X	6
26	Z	Finishing	X,Y,T	7
		Total		200

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

Then, the next calculation aims to identify the values of early start, early finish, late start, and late finish. This calculation is important because it determines the critical path of project activities. This calculation can be done using the equations found in Eq. 1, Eq. 2, Eq. 3, Eq. 4, Eq. 5, and Eq. 6 The calculation results as shown in table 2.

Table 2. CPM calculation results

No	Activity	Time (Days)	Forward		Backward		Total Float	Note
			ES	EF	LS	LF		
1	A	1	0	1	0	1	0	*Critical
2	B	1	1	2	1	2	0	*Critical
3	C	3	2	5	2	5	0	*Critical
4	D	8	5	13	5	13	0	*Critical
5	E	2	13	15	102	104	89	-
6	F	9	13	22	13	22	0	*Critical
7	G	13	22	35	22	35	0	*Critical
8	H	10	35	45	35	45	0	*Critical
9	I	7	45	52	45	52	0	*Critical
10	J	13	52	65	52	65	0	*Critical
11	K	8	65	73	65	73	0	*Critical
12	L	10	73	83	73	83	0	*Critical
13	M	13	83	96	83	96	0	*Critical
14	N	5	96	101	96	101	0	*Critical
15	O	3	101	104	101	104	0	*Critical
16	P	13	65	78	70	83	5	-

17	Q	10	78	88	83	93	5	-
18	R	10	88	98	103	113	15	-
19	S	4	98	102	113	117	15	-
20	T	13	102	115	117	130	15	-
21	U	11	88	99	93	104	5	-
22	V	4	104	108	104	108	0	*Critical
23	W	10	108	118	108	118	0	*Critical
24	X	6	118	124	118	124	0	*Critical
25	Y	6	124	130	124	130	0	*Critical
26	Z	7	137	137	130	137	0	*Critical
	Total	137						

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

The results of the experiment found clear support for the determining the critical path. Table 2 shows that the description of critical activities using the CPM method is found in activities A, B, C, D, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, V, W, X, Y, Z. The critical path completion time is 137 days. The critical path is obtained from forward calculation and backward calculation with the final result of total float equal to 0. The results demonstrated in this chapter match state of the art methods. By comparing the results from (Khatib et al., 2022; Lalmi et al., 2021; Sandstø & Reme-Ness, 2021) on project management hybrid, agile practices, and project management challenges. We hope to elaborate and add the concept of determining the critical path to the development project because the critical path is a priority path that must be done immediately without delay. Delays that occur will also have a very significant impact on the financing process and resources in the housing construction project number B9. If the delay process lasts for a long time, the financing incurred will also increase. In addition, an apparent limitation of the method is difficulty of implementing critical path scheduling as a development parameter due to field conditions that are increasingly haunted by unexpected events. Therefore, the suggestion for further researchers is to add the planning stages, especially in the scheduling method so that the possibility and accuracy of the project can be measured optimally. Overall, our method was the one that obtained the most robust results.

Program Evaluation and Review Technique (PERT)

This suggests that there are a total of 26 jobs or activities with the duration of each activity. The present study confirmed the findings about optimistic time (ot), pessimistic time (pt), and most likely time (mt). The interview results show that the ideal time range obtained in the B9 housing construction project in DM Village Banguntapan is 28 weeks or 6.5 months for most likely time (mt), 24 weeks or 5.5 months for optimistic time (ot), and 8.5 months for the pessimistic time (pt). This is an important finding in the understanding of the scheduling planning using program evaluation and review technique (PERT). Furthermore, the time duration will be based on three time components as a reference that will be used to outline the duration structure of each activity. This calculation can be done using the equations found in Eq. 7, Eq. 8, and Eq. 9. The calculation results as shown in table 3. In addition, the table also shows the activity variance and average duration.

Table 3. PERT calculation results

Activity	Durations			TE	Earliest		Latest		TF	Var	Note
	ot	mt	pt		ES	EF	LS	LF			
A	1	1	1	1	0	1	0	1	0	0	*Critical

B	1	1	1	1	1	2	1	2	0	0	*Critical
C	3	3	7	3,67	2	5,67	2	5,67	0	0,44	*Critical
D	8	8	11	8,5	5,67	14,17	5,67	14,17	0	0,25	*Critical
E	2	2	4	2,33	14,17	16,5	103,83	106,17	89,67	0,11	-
F	7	9	15	9,67	14,17	23,83	14,17	23,83	0	1,78	*Critical
G	10	13	15	12,83	23,83	36,37	23,83	36,37	0	0,69	*Critical
H	8	10	15	10,5	36,67	47,17	36,67	47,17	0	1,36	*Critical
I	5	7	12	7,5	47,17	54,67	47,17	54,67	0	1,36	*Critical
J	10	13	15	12,83	54,67	67,5	54,67	67,5	0	0,69	*Critical
K	7	8	10	8,17	67,5	75,67	67,5	75,67	0	0,25	*Critical
L	7	10	10	9,5	75,67	85,17	75,67	85,17	0	0,25	*Critical
M	10	13	15	12,83	85,17	98	85,17	98	0	0,69	*Critical
N	4	5	5	4,83	98	102,83	98	102,83	0	0,03	*Critical
O	3	3	5	3,33	102,83	106,17	102,83	106,17	0	0,11	*Critical
P	10	13	13	12,5	67,5	80	72,5	85	5	0,25	-
Q	8	10	13	10,17	80	90,17	85	95,17	5	0,69	-
R	9	10	10	9,83	90,17	100	107,5	117,33	17,33	0,03	-
S	4	4	5	4,17	100	104,17	117,33	121,5	17,33	0,03	-
T	10	13	15	12,83	104,17	117	121,5	134,33	17,33	0,69	-
U	11	11	11	11	90,17	101,17	95,17	106,17	5	0	-
V	4	4	10	5	106,17	111,17	106,17	111,17	0	1	*Critical
W	8	10	12	10	111,17	121,17	111,17	121,17	0	0,44	*Critical
X	6	6	10	6,67	121,17	127,83	121,17	127,83	0	0,44	*Critical
Y	5	6	10	6,5	127,83	134,33	127,83	134,33	0	0,69	*Critical
Z	7	7	10	7,5	134,33	141,83	134,33	141,83	0	0,25	*Critical
Total	141,83										

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

Substantially, the critical path in housing construction project number B9 occurs when it has a value of free float = total float = 0 or slack = 0. Table 3 shows that the description of critical activities using the PERT method is found in activities A, B, C, D, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, V, W, X, Y, Z. The critical path completion time is 141,83 days. The results confirm that this good choice for determine the scheduling strategy by using the critical path. Basically, all activities that pass through the critical path are advised not to be delayed. From these results, it will clearly have an impact on the duration scenario of the project scheduling process that has been determined.

The next step is to determine the calculation of probabilistic value using normal Z table using Eq. 10. The project probability value can be done after finding the results of the project variance and standard variance using Eq. 8 and Eq. 9. The data in this work consists of the total time duration (Td) is 200 days or 28.5 weeks. While the time required in the expected time (Te) in the PERT method is 141.83 or 20.2 weeks. The purpose of the calculation pattern using the weekly duration scale is to maximize the determination of the probability value in the normal distribution Z table. The calculation results of the normal Z value are in Eq. 11.

$V = \sum (PERT \text{ Critical Path})$	(11)
$= \sum (A, B, C, D, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, V, W, X, Y, Z)$	
$= \sum (10,75)$	

	$Std = \sqrt{\text{Variance Critical Path}}$
	$= \sqrt{10,75}$
	$= 3,274141 \approx 3,28$
	$Z = \frac{Td - \sum (Te PERT)}{Std}$
	$= \frac{28,5 - \sum (20,2)}{3,28}$
	$= 2,5304 \approx 2,53$

The Z Value Score calculation was able to provide a result of 2.53. The applicability of these new results is then conversion in Z Score table. The Z score conversion results show that the chance that the critical path can be completed within 141.83 days or 20.2 weeks is 0.99430 or 99% complete. Interestingly, this score can be categorized as a fantastic value because it can significantly affect the probability of project success. These basic findings are consistent with research showing that the construction of the Airlangga University parking lot building can be completed in a time duration of 340 days with a completion probability value of 99% (Syamsudin et al., 2023). This delivers significantly better results in the scheduling process because PERT method will provide gradually project success if the project follows a predetermined critical path duration standard.

Crashing Project

Extensive results conducted show that this method improves the acceleration of project duration on critical activities. In this regard, the assumption used in accelerating the project is to increase working hours (overtime). The addition of indirect costs at the crashing project stage is done by increasing the overtime duration at a cost of 600,000 IDR for all critical activities to be accelerated. The interview results show that the possible time duration to accelerate the project is 5.5 months or 168 days with a piece work concept. Together, the present findings confirm that project acceleration is performed on critical activities generated by the critical path method (CPM). Thus, project acceleration will be carried out on activities A, B, C, D, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, V, W, X, Y, Z with a normal duration on the critical path of 137 days. The calculation results of the crashing project are shown in table 4.

Table 4. Crashing project results (IDR)

Activity	Normal Day	Normal Cost	Crash Day	Crash Cost	Crash Slope	Crash By	Crashing Cost
A	1	500.000	1	500.000	0	0	0
B	1	700.000	1	700.000	0	0	0

C	3	7.200.000	2	7.800.000	600.000	1	600.000
D	8	22.202.836	6	22.802.836	300.000	2	600.000
E	2	5.325.000	2	5.325.000	0	0	0
F	9	30.285.688	7	31.171.000	442.655	2	885.310
G	13	14.538.033	10	15.138.033	200.000	3	600.000
H	10	30.285.688	8	30.885.688	300.000	2	600.000
I	7	13.250.000	5	13.850.000	300.000	2	600.000
J	13	14.538.120	10	15.138.120	200.000	3	600.000
K	8	20.259.000	7	20.859.000	600.000	1	600.000
L	10	12.405.247	8	13.005.247	300.000	2	600.000
M	13	12.680.000	11	13.280.000	300.000	2	600.000
N	5	9.400.000	4	10.000.000	600.000	0	0
O	3	2.300.000	2	2.900.000	600.000	0	0
P	13	20.731.469	13	20.731.469	200.000	0	0
Q	10	14.221.279	10	14.221.279	300.000	0	0
R	10	8.435.000	10	8.435.000	600.000	0	0
S	4	3.254.000	4	3.254.000	0	0	0
T	13	28.495.750	13	28.495.750	200.000	0	0
U	11	19.705.760	11	19.705.760	0	0	0
V	4	6.297.630	2	6.897.630	300.000	2	600.000
W	10	3.882.012	8	4.482.012	300.000	2	600.000
X	6	2.300.000	3	2.900.000	200.000	3	600.000
Y	6	1.500.000	5	2.100.000	600.000	1	600.000
Z	7	6.500.000	5	7.100.000	300.000	2	600.000
TOTAL	200	311.477.824	168	320.763.134	7.742.655	30	9.285.310

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

Our results cast a new light on accelerated projects with increasingly shorter durations. Table 4 shows that the normal cost incurred in the construction project of house number B9 at DM Village Banguntapan is 311,477,824 IDR. Meanwhile, the acceleration of time duration on the critical path shows a difference of 30 days faster than the usual time. The crashing process can save the project time duration on the critical path from 137 days to 107 days with an additional cost of 9,285,310 IDR. Therefore, total additional cost that must be incurred if the critical path is accelerated is 320,763,134 IDR with an acceleration duration of 107 days for critical activities. In this regard, other results were broadly in line with (Anugerah et al., 2021; Gu et al., 2022; Waluyo et al., 2023) on budget and time estimation in project acceleration. Another limitation in crashing project involves the issue of unstable changes in raw material prices, limited labor, and other project constraints. It is important to note, that the present evidence relies on the maturity level of the planning process and the ability to take risks to accelerate the project.

S-Curve

The results of this analysis is then vizualization with the S-curve. The S-curve are used to cumulatively record the cost and time generated by CPM, PERT, and crashing project. The results show that the application of the S Curve emphasizes the comparison of normal cost and time results with accelerated cost and time. The S-curve aims to take necessary corrective actions in optimizing the on-going project such as managing project resources and budgets to be effective during the project. The calculation of the weight on the s curve shows how much

performance contributes during the project. This project has 26 activities with a total cost of 311,477,824 IDR. In this regard, the total cost is prioritized to determine the weight of each activities. The formulation for calculating the weight on the S-curve is shown in Eq.12.

	$Weight = \frac{Project\ Activity\ Cost}{Total\ Cost} \times 100$	(12)
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Basically, the determination of the value of each project activity will be assumed by using the normal duration calculation on productivity as a form of weekly report. The visualization results of the S-curve are shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. Visualization results of the S-curve

Source: Researcher Data Processing (2024)

Planned comparisons revealed that the plan progress indicator (blue line) using normal time duration has a sloping curve shape. The sloping curve shape indicates that the project is in normal condition or all project activities can run in accordance with the predetermined time and cost calculations. Meanwhile, the crashing progress indicator (orange line) shows an upright curve shape or is higher than the plan progress curve indicator. This happens because there is an increase in the amount of duration in working hours so that the volume of work will increase and costs will increase. Thus, The increase in costs on the crashing progress indicator causes the project completion duration time to be faster and the indicator on the crashing progress will also be shorter.

5 CONCLUSION & RECOMENDATION

Broadly translated our findings indicate that 19 activities are found on the critical path. The critical path is found in activities A, B, C, D, F, G, H, I, J, K, L, M, N, O, V, W, X, Y, Z. Determination of the critical path using critical path method (CPM) can be completed in 137 days. Meanwhile, the determination of the critical path using program evaluation and review

technique (PERT) can be completed in 141.83 days with the probability value generated by the Z table showing 99% can be completed. Crashing project shows that the critical path can be accelerated with a maximum duration of 168 days. However, there is an additional project cost of 9.285.310 IDR. In this regard, the S-curve can provide an indicator that the overall project acceleration duration is 168 days at a cost of 320.763.134 IDR.

There are several limitations in time and cost optimization based on the critical path determination scenario. The main limitation is the lack of other scheduling methods, so hopefully it can expand the specific aspects of the scheduling plan. In addition, we recommend to increase the use of various theories related to scheduling projections by considering analysis of the time, cost, and labor approach. Regardless, future research could continue to explore scheduling planning that is not limited to a sector.

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